

The Psalms Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm One

10.5281/zenodo.5918683

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ How blessed is the man who does not walk in the counsel of the wicked, nor stand in the path of sinners, nor sit in the seat of scoffers!</p> <p>² But his delight is in the law of the LORD, and in His law he meditates day and night.</p> <p>³ He will be like a tree <i>firmly</i> planted by streams of water, which yields its fruit in its season and its leaf does not wither; and in whatever he does, he prospers.</p> <p>⁴ The wicked are not so, but they are like chaff which the wind drives away.</p> <p>⁵ Therefore the wicked will not stand in the judgment, nor sinners in the assembly of the righteous.</p> <p>⁶ For the LORD knows the way of the righteous, but the way of the wicked will perish.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">1 אֲשֶׁר־יֵהְיֶה אִישׁ אֲשֶׁר לֹא הָלַךְ בְּעֵצַת רְשָׁעִים וּבַדֶּרֶךְ חַטָּאִים לֹא עָמַד וּבִמְוֹשֵׁב לִצְדִים לֹא יָשָׁב: ² כִּי אִם בְּתוֹרַת יְהוָה הִפְעִיזוּ וּבְתוֹרָתוֹ יִהְיֶה יוֹמָם וּלְיָלֵלָה: ³ וְהָיָה כְּעֵץ שָׁתוּל עַל־פְּלִי מַיִם אֲשֶׁר פֵּרוֹי יִתֵּן בְּעֵתוֹ וְעֵלְהוּ לֹא־יִבּוֹל וְכֹל אֲשֶׁר־יַעֲשֶׂה יִצְלִיחַ: ⁴ לֹא־כֵן הָרְשָׁעִים כִּי אִם־כַּפְזִיץ אֲשֶׁר־תִּדְפְּנוּ רוּחַ: ⁵ עַל־כֵּן לֹא־יִקְמוּ רְשָׁעִים בַּמִּשְׁפָּט וְחַטָּאִים בַּעֲרַת צְדִיקִים: ⁶ כִּי־יִזְכַּע יְהוָה יִדְרֹךְ צְדִיקִים וְדֶרֶךְ רְשָׁעִים תִּאבֵּד:</p>

Psalm One Targum

Psa. 1:1 Happy the man who has not walked in the council of the wicked, or stood in the paths of sinners, or taken a seat in the band of mockers. ² Instead his pleasure is in the law of the LORD, and in his Torah he meditates day and night. ³ And he will be like a living tree planted by streams of water, whose fruit ripens in due course, and its leaves do not fall, and all its branches that grow ripen and flourish. ⁴ Not so the wicked; instead, they are like the chaff that the storm-wind will drive. ⁵ Therefore, the wicked will not be acquitted in the great day, nor sinners in the band of the righteous, ⁶ Because the path of the righteous is manifest in the LORD's presence, but the paths of the wicked will perish.

Psalm One Interlinear (with phonetics)

Psalms 1:1 (NAS95S)	How	blessed	is	the							
Lex		אַשֶׁר									
Lex Trl		ʾasher									
man	who	does	not	walk	in	the	counsel	of	the	wicked	Nor
אִישׁ	אֲשֶׁר	לֹא	הִלְךָ				עֵצָה			רָשָׁע	לֹא
ʾish	ʾasher	loʾ	halakh				ʿetzah			rashaʿ	loʾ
stand	in	the	path	of	sinners	Nor	sit	in	the	seat	of
עָמַד			דֶּרֶךְ		חַטָּאִים	לֹא	יָשֵׁב			מוֹשָׁב	
ʿamad			derekh		chattaʾ	loʾ	yashav			moshav	
scoffers											
לִיץ											
litz											
Psalms 1:2 (NAS95S)	But	his	delight	is	in	the	law	of	the		
Lex			חֶפְצֵךְ				תּוֹרָה				
Lex Trl			chefetz				torah				
Lord	And	in	His	law	he	meditates	day	and	night		
יְהוָה			תּוֹרָה			הֲגָה	יּוֹמָם		לַיִל		
yhwh			torah			hagah	yomam		layil		
Psalms 1:3 (NAS95S)	He	will	be	like	a	tree	firmly	planted	by		
Lex						עֵץ		שְׁתַּל			
Lex Trl						ʿetz		shatal			
streams	of	water	Which	yields	its	fruit	in	its	season	And	its
פְּלֵג		מַיִם	אֲשֶׁר	נָתַן		פְּרֵי			עֵת		
peleg		mayim	ʾasher	natan		peri			ʿet		
leaf	does	not	wither	And	in	whatever	he	does			
עֲלֵה			נָבֵל					עָשָׂה			
ʿaleh			navel					ʿasah			
he	prospers										
	צָלַח										

tzaleach

Psalms 1:4 (NAS95S) The wicked are
Lex רָשָׁע
Lex Trl rasha^c

not so But they are like chaff which the wind drives away
כֵּן מוֹץ אֲשֶׁר רוּחַ נָדַף נָדַף
ken motz ^oasher ruach nadaf nadaf

Psalms 1:5 (NAS95S) Therefore
Lex
Lex Trl

the wicked will not stand in the judgment Nor sinners
רָשָׁע קוּם מִשְׁפָּט לֹא חַטָּא
rasha^c qum mishpat lo^o chatta^o

in the assembly of the righteous
עֵדָה צְדִיק
^cedah tzaddiq

Psalms 1:6 (NAS95S) For the Lord knows the
Lex יהוה יָדַע
Lex Trl yhwh yada^c

way of the righteous But the way of the wicked will perish
דֶּרֶךְ צְדִיק דֶּרֶךְ רָשָׁע אָבַד
derekh tzaddiq derekh rasha^c ^oavad

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹ How blessed is the man who does not walk in the counsel of the wicked, nor stand in the path of sinners, nor sit in the seat of scoffers!</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"> ¹ אֲשֶׁר־יִהְיֶה אִישׁ אֲשֶׁר לֹא הִלְךָ בְּעֵצַת רְשָׁעִים וּבְדֶרֶךְ חַטָּאִים לֹא עָמַד וּבִמְוֹשֵׁב לְצִיִּים לֹא יָשָׁב : </p>

Verse Analysis

אָשַׁר (*ashar*) means “moving forward toward spiritual awareness.” Therefore, the term denotes that a person who wishes to learn about the LORD must move forward. The travel would allow the person to gain spiritual wealth, thus moving up the Ladder of Ascent from Malkhut to Yesod. Once in the Lower Waters of the Tree of Life, the Ruach of the person would continue in its spiritual learning to move toward the Sefirah Chesed. The spiritual walk toward Yesod is for the righteous.

The Sage Malbim said that this word applies to the spiritual attainment necessary for the World to Come. The World to Come defined by the Zohar and Kabbalah is the return of the Ruach to the Sefirah Yesod and beyond.

רָשָׁע (*rasha*) means “evildoer, or wicked.” This person achieves his/her goals in life by abandoning a sense of duty and honor. This person strives for the material world and has no need or desire to learn about the spiritual world.

To move forward from the material world to the spiritual world, one has to give up wanting to gain material only and turn toward the LORD and the spiritual world. Being a part of the material world is necessary because the Ruach has to live inside the Nefesh to live in the realm of Malkhut. Therefore, being successful in acquiring material things is not bad. It is when the person's attention is solely concentrated on the material world that the person can allow their spiritual development to lag or even be ignored. The Ruach will one day leave the Nefesh. The material objects accumulated during a lifetime cannot be taken into the Lower Waters of the Tree of Life. Moving forward means to be attentive to the spiritual world and the Ruach's need to learn how to move into the realm of Yesod. According to this verse, only the persons who are attempting to increase their spiritual awareness will be permitted into the Lower Waters.

The wicked are never satisfied with their material possessions because their desire is for Nefesh instant gratification. These people want physical satisfaction above everything. This gratification works well in the material world but cannot be taken into the spiritual world. This person is not concerned with what happens to the Ruach when the Nefesh dies.

חַטָּאִים (*chata*) means "sinner" but has the connotation of meaning a frivolous person.

This person scorns others using their materialism to avoid spiritual growth. This person does not believe in the LORD and that their power obtained everything they materially possess. This person places no gratitude for the LORD because the person does not believe in the LORD. The frivolous person takes a light-hearted approach toward the LORD and does not concern him/herself with the Mitzvot of the Torah.

The verse says that a righteous person must never take the advice of an evildoer (wicked) or a frivolous (sinner) person. The righteous person must not associate with potential enemies or scorners of the LORD's moral laws that are derived from the Scripture.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual development of a person is that he/she strides forward by avoiding the desires of the Nefesh and stands upright in following the LORD's Torah and does not say words against the LORD.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
² But his delight is in the law of the LORD, and in His law he meditates day and night.	² כִּי אֵם בְּתוֹרַת יְהוָה הִפְצֹו וּבְתוֹרָתוֹ יִהְיֶה יוֹמָם וּלְיָלָה׃

Verse Analysis

חִפְּצֵי (chafetz) means to “delight.” It is the striving of a person to seek spiritually driven goals, thus increasing spiritual awareness. The night is when the materialistic part of a person can rest. In ancient days most people did not work in the evening or night. Since a person is not seeking the material world in the evening, then the person can seek out the spiritual world and spiritual awareness. The study of the Torah was usually done at night because the person would not be distracted by the demands of the material world. The day is allocated for life’s tasks that are required while the Ruach resides in the Nefesh in the Sefirah Malkhut.

The Sage Hirsch said that the phrase “and in His law” or “in his Torah” did not mean the LORD’s Torah but rather the personalized Torah of the student. A person wanting to increase their spiritual awareness and climb the Ladder of Ascent needs to select his/her Torah passages to be studied. This phrase means that the person must determine which passages of the Torah must be studied to learn the spiritual lesson that

the LORD placed before him/her. The lesson learned will allow the person to gain righteousness and stride toward spiritual awareness and the spiritual world.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A person's spiritual awareness growth is found in the person's selection of the Torah to study, which is reviewed by night and practiced by day.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ He will be like a tree <i>firmly</i> planted by streams of water, which yields its fruit in its season and its leaf does not wither; and in whatever he does, he prospers.</p>	<p>וְהָיָה כְּעֵץ שְׁתוּל עַל-פְּלֵי מַיִם אֲשֶׁר פְּרִיו אֵיתָן בְּעֵתוֹ וְעָלְהוּ לֵא- יָבוּל וְכָל אֲשֶׁר-יַעֲשֶׂה יִצְלִיחַ׃</p>

Verse Analysis

שְׁתוּל (*shatool*) means “replanted.” Young shoots of a tree are taken from the original tree and are replanted to grow new trees. When a materialistic world person becomes aware of the spiritual world, they need to be replanted. One reason is that the newfound spiritual awareness needs nourishment for the Ruach’s development and character. These needs are beyond the environment of the Nefesh that the Ruach was born into. Many times this replanting must occur if the Ruach cannot find what it needs to expand and grow into the spiritual world. Sometimes this means going to a religious school or Yeshiva, or perhaps to a mentor or spiritual director.

The choice of brooks is when the person selects the best environment for study. Sometimes the first brook that is selected turns out not to be the best brook. Then the person will need to seek out a new place of study. Of course, the first place selected may be adequate until the person reaches a particular rung on the Ladder of Ascent, then a different environment may be necessary to continue the climb to Chesed.

Being replanted can mean being taken out of the material world and placed into the spiritual world. The person is planted into the material world when born. The movement to the spiritual world is the replanting of the person. Once a person moves to the spiritual world, it must always be spiritual feed.

עַל-פְּלִיגֵי מַיִם (al gal'gae mayim) means “by streams of water” and says that there are numerous branches of study that a person can take. However, all the branches of study spring from the same source. The source is the LORD’s Torah. The Torah is the source of all thinking and learning of the spiritual world.

The leaf protects the Ruach while it is developing while the fruit is the Ruach. The Torah can be considered the leaf because following the mitzvot of the Torah, the Nefesh is protected, and the Ruach can obtain spiritual nourishment.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

One who becomes spiritually aware is one who has one foot in the material world and one foot in the spiritual world and draws spiritual strength from it and becomes righteous as a result of living in both worlds.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
⁴ The wicked are not so, but they are like chaff which the wind drives away.	לֹא־כֵן הַרְשָׁעִים כִּי אִם־כַּפְזִיץ אֲשֶׁר־תִּדְבְּנוּ רוּחַ:

Verse Analysis

The wicked are lawless people who are only concerned with material gains in the material world. They are not righteous in their attitudes and conducts. They do not understand that there is much more to the LORD's world than just materialism.

A grain stalk is composed of three items:

1. The kernel is for human consumption
2. The straw is for animal consumption
3. The chaff initially protects the grain but is useless when the grain matures

The chaff contained the goodness which was given to the kernel and the straw. Besides, the chaff protected the grain.

The materialistic person, when born, has goodness in them and the ability to develop spiritually but gave it up for the desires of the Nefesh. The Spirit of the LORD will destroy the person who lives only in the material world. The materialistic person had their ethical goodness removed because of their desires of the Nefesh. These are people

who do not follow the mitzvot of the LORD from the Torah. The Spirit of the LORD will destroy that Ruach by disregarding it when it attempts to return to Yesod and the Lower Waters.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The materialistic person had all their ethical goodness removed, and the Spirit of the LORD disregards the person.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ Therefore the wicked will not stand in the judgment, nor sinners in the assembly of the righteous.</p>	<p>⁵ עַל-כֵּן לֹא-יִקְמוּ רְשָׁעִים בְּמִשְׁפַּט יְחֻטְּאִים בְּעֵרַת צְדִיקִים :</p>

Verse Analysis

מִשְׁפַּט (*mesh'fat*) means “divine judgment over the deeds of people.” Judgment originates in the Sefirah Gevurah. The persons who are sinners do not repent of their sins. The LORD gives time between a sin and a punishment so that the person can recognize the sin and offer repentance. When sinners refuse to repent for their sins, the divine judgment of Gevurah will not deal with them. It means that their Ruach will not be able to return to Yesod because they are filled with unrepented sin.

רְשָׁעִים (*r'shaym*) means a person who seeks neither inner nor outer support from the LORD’s moral law which has been revealed; rather these persons allow themselves to be swayed only by their passions and the environmental temptations of the material world. They will be unable to rise up or stand up at the time of divine judgment.

The Zohar says that when divine judgment occurs, the person who repented for sins and has at least performed one mitzvah throughout their life will come into the Lower Waters. The repented sins are forgotten by the LORD. At that divine time, the Accuser will come before the LORD with a list of the sins that the person had done. The LORD

will tell the Accuser to leave because the sins are no longer with the person because the person repented.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The people who do not believe in the LORD shall not be forgiven and will not join the righteous in the Lower Waters of the Tree of Life.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 For the LORD knows the way of the righteous, but the way of the wicked will perish.	6 עַל-כֵּן לֹא-יִקְמוּ רְשָׁעִים בַּמִּשְׁפָּט וְחַטָּאִים בְּעֵרַת צְדִיקִים :

Verse Analysis

The way of the righteous is that they walk their entire life following the LORD's intent for all humankind and will not allow them to perish. The Zohar says that there is at least one righteous person in all generations. The righteous persons are a reminder to the LORD that the people of the Earth need the LORD's help to change from their materialistic ways to righteous ways.

צְדִיקִים (*tzdeekym*) means “that the righteous can be sure of their progress toward salvation because the LORD through the Shekinah will direct the righteous.” The Shekinah will be available to help the righteous in their path so that when the Nefesh dies, the Ruach will be able to return to Yesod and the Lower Waters.

The people who are lawless will not receive any particular divine intervention.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the LORD assists the righteous on their way toward salvation while the materialistic only people are doomed.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

¹ The spiritual development of a person is that he/she strides forward by avoiding the desires of the Nefesh and stands upright in following the LORD's Torah and does not say words against the LORD.

² A person's spiritual awareness growth is found in the person's selection of the Torah to study, which is reviewed by night and practiced by day.

³ One who becomes spiritually aware is one who has one foot in the material world and one foot in the spiritual world and draws spiritual strength from it and becomes righteous as a result of living in both worlds.

⁴ The materialistic person had all their ethical goodness removed, and the Spirit of the LORD disregards the person.

⁵ The people who do not believe in the LORD shall not be forgiven and will not join the righteous in the Lower Waters of the Tree of Life.

⁶ For the LORD assists the righteous on their way toward salvation while the materialistic only people are doomed.

Lessons from the Psalm

1. The return of the Ruach to join its soul mate is imperative
2. People need to learn the ways of the Torah
3. To please the LORD, a person must follow the mitzvot

Definitions

Zohar - “The Zohar (Hebrew זֹהָר; Splendor, radiance) is widely considered the most important work of Kabbalah, Jewish mysticism. It is a mystical commentary on the Torah (five books of Moses), written in medieval Aramaic and medieval Hebrew. It contains a mystical discussion of the nature of God, the origin and structure of the universe, the nature of souls, sin, redemption, good and evil, and related topics. The Zohar is not one book, but a group of books. These books include scriptural interpretations as well as material on theosophic theology, mythical cosmogony, mystical psychology, and what some would call anthropology.” Source: <https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/the-zohar>

Kabbalah – “Kabbalah (also spelled Kabalah, Cabala, Qabala)—sometimes translated as “mysticism” or “occult knowledge—is a part of Jewish tradition that deals with the essence of God. Whether it entails a sacred text, an experience, or the way things work, Kabbalists believe that God moves in mysterious ways. However, Kabbalists also believe that true knowledge and understanding of that inner, mysterious process is obtainable, and through that knowledge, the greatest intimacy with God can be attained.” Source: <https://reformjudaism.org/what-kabbalah>

The Tree of Life

“**Isaac ben Solomon Luria**, byname **Ha-ari** (Hebrew: The Lion), (born 1534, Jerusalem, Palestine, Ottoman Empire—died August 5, 1572, Safed, Syria [now Zefat, Israel]), eponymous founder of the Lurianic school of Kabbala (Jewish esoteric mysticism). Source:

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Isaac-ben-Solomon-Luria>

Samson Hirsch - It has often been said that Orthodox Judaism has always existed since the Jews received the Torah on Mt. Sinai and that Conservative Judaism was a reaction to Reform Judaism, however, that is not entirely accurate. In fact, modern Orthodoxy did not exist until the reforms and innovations of Rabbi Samson Raphael Hirsch.

Hirsch was born in 1808 in Hamburg, Germany. He went to the public schools, where he was strongly influenced by Schiller and Hegel, and received his Jewish education at home. His father was an observant Jew. His grandfather, Mendel Frankfurter, was the founder of the Talmud Torah in Hamburg. Through the education of his teachers, considered German Jewry's greatest Talmudists, who were proficient in both non-Jewish and Jewish culture, Hirsch decided to train for the rabbinate with the aim of demonstrating that traditional Judaism and Western culture are compatible with each other. From 1823 to 1829 he studied under Rabbi Jacob Ettlinger, a distinguished German Jewish Talmudist. He then entered the University of Bonn. While at Bonn one of his classmates was Abraham Geiger, who later became a leader of the Reform movement. At Bonn, he studied classical languages, history and philosophy. Source: <https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/samson-raphael-hirsch>

Sefer Yetzirah “(Hebrew: ספר יצירה *Sēpher Yəṣîrâh*, *Book of Formation*, or *Book of Creation*) is the title of the earliest extant book on Jewish mysticism, although some early commentators treated it as a treatise on mathematical and linguistic theory as opposed to Kabbalah. *Yetzirah* is more literally translated as "Formation"; the word *Briah* is used for "Creation". The book is traditionally ascribed to the patriarch Abraham, although others attribute its writing to Rabbi Akiva. Modern scholars have not reached consensus on the question of its origins. According to Rabbi Saadia Gaon, the objective of the book's author was to convey in writing how the things of our universe came into existence.

The famous opening words of the book are as follows:

By thirty-two mysterious paths of wisdom Jah has engraved [all things], [who is] the Lord of hosts, the God of Israel, the living God, the Almighty God, He that is uplifted and exalted, He that Dwells forever, and whose Name is holy; having created His world

by three [derivatives] of [the Hebrew root-word] *šḥr*: namely, *sefer* (a book), *sefor* (a count) and *sippur* (a story), along with ten calibrations of empty space, twenty-two letters [of the Hebrew alphabet], [of which] three are principal [letters] (i.e. **ש מ א**), seven are double-sounding [consonants] (i.e. **בג״ד כפר״ת**) and twelve are ordinary [letters] (i.e. **ה ו ז ח ט י ל נ ס ע צ ק**).” Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sefer_Yetzirah

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

